

**JOURNAL OF
THE INTERNATIONAL ASSOCIATION
FOR SHELL AND SPATIAL
STRUCTURES**

FORMERLY BULLETIN OF THE INTERNATIONAL ASSOCIATION FOR SHELL AND SPATIAL STRUCTURES

Prof. D. h-C Eng .E. TORROJA, founder

Vol. 46 (2005) n.2
August n.148

Journal

VOL. 46 (2005) n.2

n. 148 August

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A SELF-STRESS MAINTENING FOLDING TENSEGRITY SYSTEM BY FINITE MECHANISM ACTIVATION

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Editor's Note: Manuscript submitted 30 March 2005; revision received 7 June 2005; accepted for publication 20 June 2005. This paper is open for written discussion, which should be submitted to the IASS Secretariat no later than April 2006.

ABSTRACT

As a general rule, the folding of tensegrity systems occurs by removing and/or keeping self-stress in the structure. In this article, we will concentrate on the folding of tensegrity systems which keeps self-stress throughout the folding process. Finite mechanisms are used for this folding procedure, and the stability of the various members is ensured by self-stress effect within the structure throughout the process (this has been verified by real scaled models and computer aided simulations). The results found have demonstrated that one can act on part of the structure without affecting the structure as a whole. It is therefore possible to fold the grid as a whole or in part. The study of the fundamental folding characteristics has enabled us generalize this process to other tensegrity grids with double curvature, when some finite mechanisms can be activated.

Keywords: *Tensegrity, folding, unfolding, variable geometry, finite mechanisms, self-stress.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The architectural function of foldable tensegrity systems is of first interest, and it is characterized by several parameters. As architectural component flexibility, adaptability between outside and inside, ease of use, aesthetics and practicality are the fundamental parameters [1]. For all applications, the folding process is a fundamental step in the study of various geometric configurations; it is also necessary to describe the introduction of possible finite mechanisms.

The folding of tensegrity systems has remained for most researchers [2], the reverse process of the stiffening of the system as a stable structure. Finite mechanisms and self-stress are the two faces of a same problematic. The mechanism is activated by removing self-stress, by way of shortening the bars or lengthening the cables (modifying the s/c characteristic ratio for regular systems (s : bar length c : cable length)) [3].

The folding process which involves the removal of self-stress is dual of the process of tensegrity systems creation. But it is possible to fold tensegrity systems without having to remove completely the self-stress: the process is then dependant upon the intrinsic foldable characteristics of the structure. Finite mechanisms can be introduced while keeping a partial self-stress throughout the folding procedure.

The presence of finite mechanisms is made possible by a specific assembly of the structural members: degrees of freedom have to be carefully studied. In this case, self-stress is kept in the folding process but the consequences on the structural behavior have to be taken into account [4].

This strategy has enabled us to develop an approach in the design of mechanisms in which the folding process relies on self-stress. We have applied this approach on several structural configurations, and in particular, on double layer tensegrity grids.

2. INTRODUCTION OF FINITE MECHANISMS AND SELF-STRESS KEEPING THROUGHOUT THE FOLDING PROCEDURE

In this paragraph we will look at tensegrity systems which can be folded while remaining in a state of self-stress throughout the folding process. Our research in this field has led us to explore different systems and their behavior, focusing on various possible states of self-stress and finite mechanisms for tensegrity systems. In order to research the basic concepts related to this study, we describe the various states of self-stress and finite mechanisms for a basic module of a tensegrity grid. The description of the studied grid can be done at least according to three different elementary components: 2v spacer (a), truss beam (b) and cubic module (c) (Figure 1). This modular decomposition enables, on one hand to understand the structural behavior of the grid, and on the other hand to adopt a strategy for the folding process. Amongst these elementary components, we had a particular interest for the basic cubic module (c in figure 1), for its capacity to be folded while remaining in a state of self-stress.

Figure 1. Structural components of the tensegrity grid: (a) 2v (spacers); (b) truss beam; (c) cubic module

2.1. Basic cubic module

The basic cubic module (Figure 2) with 4 bars and 12 cables is a regular tensegrity system without stable self stress when it is considered alone, but with an assembly of four modules a state of self-stress is achieved.

Figure 2. Basic cubic module geometry.

The basic cubic module's geometry consists of 8 triangular systems which are assembled in pairs to form a cube. In this assembly two parallel quadrangular faces are not triangulated (1-5-2-7 and 9-10-6-8). This elementary observation leads to two possible finite mechanisms. The first mechanism is a movement by “shear action”, keeping horizontal the quadrangular face 8-9-6-10. The target folding plane is defined by the square 1-9-5-10 (Figure 3a,c). All the lateral faces are not distorted in this displacement. The second mechanism is a rotation around the Y axis of the face 8-7-2-6 mapping it on to the target folding plane (Figure 3b, d). Only the first mechanism which folds the system by “shear” action is suitable, and we have therefore concentrated our attention on this particular mechanism (Figure 3c).

Figure 3. Basic cubic module mechanism, (a,b) initial configuration, (c) mechanism $m=1$ (shear action), (d) mechanism $m=2$ (rotation motion)

2.2. Folding of a 9-module grid

The geometric configuration illustrated in figure 4 is a grid generated by a bidirectional assembly of the same module. Since the grid is made up with the same cubic module, the folding process, as illustrated above, should be activated by shear forces.

Mechanically, the system has six no conform states of self-stress (conformity is dependent upon the unilateral stiffness of components). The mechanisms are based on the transformation in diamond shape of the cubes that generate the grid. The system contains ten finite mechanisms whose direction varies in accordance with the horizontal plane. The number of finite mechanisms varies according to the boundary conditions of the structure.

Figure 4. 9-module double layer tensegrity grid

We will demonstrate later that by replacing the edge struts with a peripheral cable, we can alter the number of finite mechanisms and therefore the number of folding possibilities for the structure.

All mechanisms are linked to the main orthogonal directions of the grid. Three modes can be identified.

Mode 1

This process acts on a vertical folding plane, which corresponds to one of the four vertical edges of the grid. The struts which are initially parallel to the folding plane get closer and closer together, following a zig-zag path (figure 5). In the resulting position, four squares are mapped on the folding plane.

Mode 2

This method is also a folding process on to a vertical folding plane; however in this case the parallel trusses flatten all in the same direction. This is a global shear mechanism for the grid. As a result there are six squares on the target folding plane. (Figure 6).

Mode 3

This method consists in flattening the corner modules on to the central module. The shapes of the central module and of the corner modules are not affected (Figure 7) The vertical edges of the central modules are the four rotation axis. In this process the four median edge cubic modules are folded: during this shear process one of their lateral faces is flattened on the opposite one, which is simultaneously one of the faces of the central module. The other face is mapped upon its common face with the corresponding corner cube

Figure 5. 9 basic cubic module assembly, (a) unfolded configuration, (b) intermediary configuration, (c) folded configuration

Figure 6. *Mode 2:* 9 basic module assembly, (a) unfolded configuration, (b) intermediary configuration, (c) folded configuration.

Figure 7. *Mode 3:* 9 basic module assembly, (a) unfolded configuration, (b) intermediary configuration, (c) folded configuration.

2.3. Folding of basic 9 module with a peripheral cable

The folding methods described in the preceding paragraphs lead to the development of a folding method applied to a grid system using a peripheral cable. The edge struts of the grid (Figure 4) are replaced by a cable which braces together the two layers of the grid (Figure 8). This new grid structural composition has of course a consequence on the number of finite mechanisms, and simultaneously on the folding process.

Figure 8. *grid with 9 basic cubic modules, with peripheral cable, (a) top view, (b) axonometric view*

Concerning the finite mechanisms, the edge row modules ((I, II, III), (VII, VIII, IX), (I, IV, VII),

(III, VI, IX) do not allow any folding mechanisms as the peripheral cable braces the structure at its 4 corners (I, III, VII and IX). But the two central line modules ((IV, V, VI), (II, V, VII)) still hold horizontal finite mechanisms. There also exists the global mechanism by which all 8 modules (I, II, III, IV, VI, VII, VIII and IX) can rotate around the central module V. We therefore have two folding modes compatible with these finite mechanisms. They respectively correspond to the previous so-called “Mode 1” and “Mode 3”

Mode 1

Using the folding process illustrated in Figure 9, the system folds and the outer edge modules remain unfolded. With few modifications we can fold the whole structure. These modifications will be described in another paragraph.

Mode 3

This mode is identical to mode 3, which has been illustrated in Figure 7. If the nodes of the central module are all fixed, the system has one finite mechanism which can be described on the horizontal plane (Figure 10).

Figure 9. computer modeling of the folding process of a basic 9 module system according to mode 1. Respectively (a,b and c) top view, (d,e and f) axonometric view.

Figure 10. Folding process of the grid according to mode 3. Top view of (a, b and c), axonometric view (d, e and f)

2.4. Compatibility relationship between edge modules

The grids described in the preceding paragraphs are regular: no specific lengths or angles are prescribed. By imposing geometric constraints we can make some improvements. The geometric constraints for mode 1 act on modules II and VIII, for mode 3 on modules II, IV, VI, VIII.

By this way we will introduce geometric compatibility conditions in order to reduce the system at its most compact state. Simultaneously we still keep partial self stress during the folding process.

Mode 1

The system illustrated in figure 11 consists of 9 modules two of which, namely modules IV and VI can not be folded in the final configuration. This is due do the relationship that exists in the given geometric configuration of the edge modules; in particular values of angles α and β may play a descriptive role. In the folded configuration of the initial system (Figure 11 a-d) the modules 11 and VIII flatten on the folding plane with $\alpha = 0^\circ$ and $\beta=0^\circ$ at the end of the process. But modules IV and VI do not fold. We therefore modify the length of some edges in modules II and VIII in such a way as to make $\alpha = 0^\circ$ and $\beta=180^\circ$ in the final folded configuration (Figure 11e-h). The modules flatten and fold onto themselves, since the modules I, III, VII and IX flatten in the same direction thanks to the unilaterality of the cable that links them on 4 corners.

Mode 3

For this mode, it is necessary to establish a relationship which enables all 4 modules to flatten around the central module. In order to achieve this, modules II, IV, VI and VIII must have angles $\alpha = 0^\circ$ and $\beta = -90^\circ$ at the end of the process. For both folding methods, the relationship between angles α and β is:

$$(l_1 + \varepsilon)^2 + l_1^2 - 2 \times (l_1 + \varepsilon) \times l_1 \times \cos(\alpha - \beta) + 2 \times l_2 \times (\cos \beta \times l_1 - \cos \alpha \times (l_1 + \varepsilon)) = 0$$

Figure 11. Geometric compatibility of two modes; (a)-(d) top view of initial configurations (e)-(h) geometric configuration during the folding process according to mode 1. (i)-(l) according to mode 3

2.5. Results found and critical observations

This part is related to the mechanical description of the structural behavior during the folding process. This evolution is described using the numeric simulation called Tensegrité2000, developed in our laboratory.

Chosen Hypothesis:

For mode 1, the system is made of 9 modules, a force is applied on joint 7 in the y-direction in order to activate a shear mechanism, the system is reticulated and degrees of freedom are fixed for half of the system. Nodes 12, 15 and 16 are respectively fixed for the x-y-z directions, xy and xz axis(Figure 12). The result of the virtual simulation of the mechanism is given in the upper part of the figure (plane view, mode 1)

For mode 3, some other nodes are fixed to establish the central module in a stable position, the edge modules are activated by a force applied on node 6.

The new position of the modules is characterized by the angle α with the y axis. This is the parameter of the evolution. In the initial unfolded configuration, the system has one conform state of self-stress (compression in struts and tension in cables). At

each stage of the folding process, according to the above hypothesis, internal forces have been calculated for all of the elements; displacements of the nodes are also computed. During the folding process, the number of states of self-stress is not modified, but its level is altered (Figure 13).

Figure 12. Screen caption of the grid taken from the T2000 program

We have noticed that the internal forces in the vertical cables (which are a part of the “spacers”) is never increasing too much during the folding process. This is due to the fact that the cables are orthogonal to the direction of the finite mechanisms.

Figure 13. Variations in the degree of self-stress throughout the folding process, (a) according to mode 1, (b) according to mode 3

2.6. Prototype

We have tested our proposal on a real physical model of the grid and we could check our design.

We have designed two kinds of nodes:

- Those of the fixed truss: these nodes do not allow any relative rotation around their vertical axis.
- Those of the pivoting parts: the nodes have

been designed so as to allow a relative rotation of components around the vertical axis. (Figure 14 b,c).

A model of this node has been realized in order to ensure that it could be activated under lateral action exerted, and that it does not lock when the structure is folded (due to friction between the parts).

The design takes this aspect into account by aligning the nodes on the mean fiber of the struts so as to decrease this friction problem (Figure 15).

Figure 14. Intermediary rotation joint, (a) axonometric view, (b) unfolded configuration (top view), (folded configuration (top view)

Figure 15. Rotation joints aligned according to the internal efforts and the grid geometry

Figure 16. Folding of the grid by flattening the truss beams

3. CONCLUSION

In this paper we have looked at new configurations where during the folding process, the tensegrity structure remains in a state of self-stress because of finite mechanisms which are activated. We used several models and finally we verified our hypothesis on a physical model

As a rule, folding tensegrity systems involves keeping and/or removing self-stress (by introducing finite mechanisms). Accordingly, self-stress is achieved during all the stages of the folding process (this has been confirmed by a physical model and computer simulations). We have also demonstrated that the folding process can be applied totally or in part only.

This study, developed for a plane tensegrity grid, has opened a wide range of possibilities for folding double curved (positive or/and negative curvature) tensegrity systems, which generalize the case of the double layer grid.

The main feature is that all these examples (developed in the thesis by Smaili [1]) are based on finite mechanisms existence. One example among others is given in Figure 17.

At the end, this study has to be considered as a geometric investigation which is useful because it does not require self stress cancellation. But it is also obvious that it has some drawbacks like a final volume which is not significantly reduced. But this kind of folding can be suitable for some applications even if the scale of the system and the possible applications are not defined at this stage. The total volume reduction is not always the objective: a mapping on plane can also be required.

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Figure 17. (a) radiating planes converging in one point (top view), (b) elementary portion in which P_1 and P_2 converge in one point (axonometric view), (c) radiating planes converging in several points, (d) geometric compatibility of 2 portions of different sizes